

Perceived organizational control, moral disengagement and workplace deviance

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ABSTRACT

Extant research has suggested that perceived organisational control and moral disengagement influence workplace deviance, but relatively little research has examined the incremental validity of perceived organisational control on workplace deviance after controlling for moral disengagement. To address this void in literature, the present study is an attempt to examine whether perceived organisational control accounts for incremental variance in workplace deviance, after controlling for moral disengagement. We used a sample of 256 teaching staff from Federal Polytechnic Bida, Nigeria. We also used Hierarchical multiple regression analysis along with descriptive analysis and correlation analysis to examine the relationships among the key constructs. Overall, results suggest that moral disengagement accounted for a significant amount of variance relative to perceived organisational control. In conclusion, moral disengagement has a significant role to play in predicting workplace deviance. A morally disengaged staff member will engage in more deviant acts. Hence, there is a need for human resource policies and strategies to curtail workplace deviance and put employees under checks.

Keywords: incremental validity moral disengagement, organisational control, workplace deviance

Introduction

Over the past three decades, workplace deviance has emerged as an important construct of interest among researchers, practitioners and policy-makers (de Lara & Tacoronte, 2017; Diefendorff & Mehta, 2017; Kura, Shamsudin, & Chauhan, 2013b; Kura, Shamsudin, & Chauhan, 2015). This growing interest in workplace deviance is due to the negative consequences of such behaviours for both organisation and its members (Lawrence & Robinson, 2017; Spector & Fox, 2012). According to Robinson and Bennett (1995), workplace deviance refers to a voluntary behavior that violates significant organizational norms and in so threatens the well-being of an organisation, its members, or both (p.556). Anecdotal evidence

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and some empirical research have documented the negative consequences of workplace deviance for both organisation and its members. For example, in the United States (U.S.), the use of drugs and alcohol in the workplace has been reported to have important negative consequences in increasing workplace injuries, turnover and absenteeism, as well as decreasing worker productivity, among others (U. S. Department of Health and Human Services, 2008). Research also highlights that victims of interpersonal deviance (i.e., deviant behavior directed at individuals) are more likely to experience job stress, low morale, decrease in productivity, as well as increase in fear and insecurity in the workplace (Henle, Giacalone, & Jurkiewicz, 2005). Research further indicates that workplace deviance has indirect costs to organisations, in terms of reduced labour productivity (Bowling & Gruys, 2010; Johnson, 2009), lowered organizational commitment (Gardner & Johnson, 2001), higher rates of turnover (Namie, 2017), and damaged organizational growth, and profitability, among others (Lee & Ok, 2014). Workplace deviance is largely studied according to whether such behaviour is targeted against employing organisation, its members, or both (Berry, Ones, & Sackett, 2017; Hastings & O'Neill, 2009; Henle et al., 2005; Kura et al., 2015; Lim, 2012; Mulki, Jaramillo, & Locander, 2006; Shamsudin, 2003).

A large volume of empirical research has been carried out to uncover the underlying causes of workplace deviance. To date, some of the factors that have been studied in relation to workplace deviance include perceived organizational justice (Aquino, Lewis, & Bradfield, 1999; Colquitt, Conlon, Wesson, Porter, & Ng, 2001; Near & Miceli, 2013; Shao, Rupp, Skarlicki, & Jones, 2013), perceived organizational support (Eder & Eisenberger, 2008; Ferris, Brown, & Heller, 2009; O'Reilly & Chatman, 1986), and psychological contract breach (Bandura, 1977; Jensen, Opland, & Ryan, 2010; Restubog, Bordia, & Tang, 2017; Zhao,

Wayne, Glibkowski, & Bravo, 2017). Despite the abundance of research on workplace deviance, to date organisational researchers has offered no theoretical explanation as to incremental validity of perceived organisational control after controlling for moral disengagement in predicting workplace deviance. To address this void, the present study has examined the incremental validity of perceived organisational control after controlling for moral disengagement among teaching staff of Federal Polytechnic Bida, Nigeria.

Theory and hypotheses

Perceived organizational control and workplace deviance

While the workplace deviance construct has gained a lot of momentum for several decades now, literatures indicate a lack of agreement regarding not only the terminology used, but also the definition offered of what is considered to be a similar construct (Robinson & Bennett, 1997). For example, researchers have given different names to the workplace deviance construct including, antisocial behaviour (Giacalone & Greenberg, 1997), delinquency (Hogan & Hogan, 1989), employee theft (Greenberg, 1990), workplace sabotage (Analoui, 1995; Harris & Ogbonna, 2006), workplace incivility (Andersson & Pearson, 1999), workplace aggression (Baron & Kenny, 1996), worker resistance (Thompson & Ackroyd, 1995), and cyber loafing (Lim, 2012). Although different terminologies are used, using different theoretical perspectives, organizational behaviour researchers seemingly agree that such behaviour could bring harm to both individuals and organization (Shamsudin, Chauhan, & Kura, 2014).

On the other hand, organizational control refers to the processes of influencing the behaviour of people as members of a formal organization with the goal of increasing the probability that they will achieve organizational goals (Wilkes, Srinivasan, & Flamholtz,

2005). Prior research has established positive relationship between perceived organisational control and various forms of workplace deviance. Specifically, Kura, Shamsudin, and Chauhan (2013a) showed that lack of organizational formal control increases the likelihood of employee deviant behaviour at work. Relatedly, disciplinary practices instituted by organisations have been found to be associated with decrease in cyber loafing (de Lara, Tacoronte, & Ding, 2006). From theoretical perspective, organisational control theory (Flamholtz, Das, & Tsui, 1985), postulates that formal control systems instituted by organisations play an important role in aligning the behaviour of employees with the organizational goals.

Moral disengagement and workplace deviance

Moral disengagement has been defined as an individual's propensity to evoke cognitions which restructure one's actions to appear less harmful, minimize one's understanding of responsibility for one's actions, or attenuate the perception of the distress one causes others (Moore, 2008). Several scholars (Tenbrunsel & Smith-Crowe, 2008) have suggested that organisational researchers should attend to the role of cognitive processes in explaining deviant behaviour at work. Extant empirical studies have shown that moral disengagement relates to various forms of deviant behaviour at work. For example, in line with the principle of moral disengagement theory, Claybourn (2011) reported a significant positive relationship between moral disengagement and workplace harassment. The author further contended that employees who reported relatively high tendencies for moral disengagement also were more likely to report having been subjected to more negative behaviours at work than those who reported low levels of moral disengagement (Claybourn, 2011). In a related study, Christian and Ellis (2014) established a significant and positive relationship between dissatisfaction and

deviant behaviour at work among 429 support personnel in Malaysian public service organizations. Moral disengagement theory also postulates that employees who are morally disengaged have higher tendency to engage in behaviour that harms an organisation, its members, or both (Bandura, 1986; Bandura, 1999; Robinson & Bennett, 1995). Drawing on organisational control theory and the theory of moral disengagement, we contended that laxity of organisational formal control increases workplace deviance by encouraging employees to morally disengage. Therefore, based on the above empirical evidence and theoretical perspectives described previously, the following hypothesis is advanced:

Hypothesis 1: Perceived organisational control has incremental validity beyond moral disengagement in predicting workplace deviance.

Method

Participants

This study employed a cross-sectional research design. Participants were 256 teaching staff from Federal Polytechnic Bida, Nigeria.

Measures

Perceived organizational control

To measure perceived organisational control, four items were adapted from de Lara, Tacoronte, and Ding's (2006) formal organisational controls scale. Each item used in formal organizational controls scale was rated based on 6-point Likert scale, ranging from 1-Strongly disagree to 6 Strongly agree. Sample items are –I perceive the proper use of my work tools maybe checked by my polytechnic. I may be accused at any moment of not strictly fulfilling my job obligations.

Moral disengagement

Moral disengagement was measured using 8-item Boardley and Kavussanu's (2008) moral disengagement scale. This scale has been found to be a reliable and valid measure of moral disengagement (Boardley & Kavussanu, 2009; Stanger, Kavussanu, Boardley, & Ring, 2013; Tractlet, Moret, Ohl, & Clémence, 2015). In the present study, responses were made on a 6-point Likert scale (1=strongly disagree and 6=strongly agree). Sample items are "It is okay for a lecturer to work on a personal matter instead of work for his/her polytechnic". "It is unfair to make an ethnic, religious, or racial remark or joke at work".

Workplace deviance

Workplace deviance was assessed using Bennett and Robinson's (2000) measure of workplace deviance. Although this scale suggests two underlying dimensions of workplace deviance, we followed the procedure adopted in the prior research (Lee & Allen, 2012) by collapsing these two dimensions into a unidimensional scale. Thus, eleven items were adapted to measure workplace deviance. Participants respond to each statement using a 6-point Likert scale (1=strongly disagree or 6=strongly agree). Sample items are "Publicly embarrass someone at work"; "Come in late to class without permission".

Data Analysis Strategy

To assess the incremental validity of the perceived organisational control relative to moral disengagement in predicting workplace deviance, we used a hierarchical linear regression to test our hypothesis in two steps. In the first step, perceived organisational control was entered into the Predictive Analytics Software's regression analysis menu. We then entered the moral disengagement in the second step to ensure any observed effects for the perceived

organisational control was not due to shared variance with other variable (i.e., moral disengagement).

Results

Means, Standard Deviations, and Correlations of the Study Variables:

The descriptive statistics, which comprised means, standard deviations, scale reliabilities, and correlations among the study variables, are presented in Table 2. As shown in Table 2, perceived organizational control was negatively associated with workplace deviance ($r = -.866$; $p < .001$). Conversely, moral disengagement was positively related to workplace deviance ($r = .876$; $p < .001$). Regarding the scale reliabilities, Table 2 shows that all constructs had alpha values above .70, which well exceeded the recommended thresholds of 0.70 (Nunnally, 1978). Hence, Table 2 suggested a high level of internal consistency reliabilities. Finally, Table 2 shows that among the constructs, workplace deviance had the highest mean ($M = 4.595$, $SD = 1.354$), followed by moral disengagement ($M = 4.184$, $SD = 1.300$), and then perceived organisational control ($M = 2.529$, $SD = 1.344$). All items were measured on a six-point scale.

Table 1
 Respondents' Demographic Statistics

	Frequency	Percentage
Gender		
Male	164	64.1
Female	92	35.9
Age group		
21-30 years	8	3.1
31-40 years	77	30.1
41-50 years	81	31.6
51 years and above	90	35.2
Marital status		
Married	147	57.4
Single	109	42.6

Educational level		
BachelorDegree	60	23.4
HigherNationalDiploma	130	50.8
Masters	60	23.4
Others	6	2.3

Table2
 Descriptive Statistics, Scale Reliabilities and Correlations of the Study Variables

		Mean	SD	1	2	3
1	Perceivedorganisational control	2.529	1.344	.910		
2	Moraldisengagement	4.184	1.300	-.894**	.938	
3	Workplace deviance	4.595	1.354	-.866**	.876**	.960

Note. **. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (1-tailed). Entries shown in bold diagonal represents the Scale Reliabilities.

Incremental Validity of perceived organisational control and moral disengagement on workplace deviance: As shown in Table 3, the Hierarchical regressions demonstrated that perceived organisational control significantly predicted workplace deviance in a negative direction. Conversely, moral disengagement was found to be significantly and positively related to workplace deviance. The results further established that moral disengagement is the main predictor of workplace deviance ($\beta=.505;p<0.01$) relative to perceived organizational control ($\beta=-.415; p<0.01$). Additionally, the results suggest that perceived organisational control accounted for an additional 75% of the variance in workplace deviance ($p<0.001$). Controlling for the moral disengagement, significantly accounted for 80% of explained variance in the second step forwork place deviance.

Table3

Hierarchical multiple regression analyses predicting workplace deviance from perceived organisational control and moral disengagement (n=256)

Predictor	B	SE	B
Step1			
Intercept	6.802	.090	
Perceived organisational control	-.872	.032	-.866***
Step2			
Intercept	3.453	.421	
Perceived organisational control	-.418	.063	-.415***
Moral disengagement	.526	.065	.505***
		Step1	Step2
R Square		.750	.802
AdjustedRSquare		.749	.800
F		763.915	511.992
Sig		.000	.000

Note.**Regression is significant at the 0.01level(1-tailed)

Discussionandconclusion:

The goal of the present study was to examine the incremental validity of perceived organisational control and moral disengagement in predicting workplace deviance among teaching staff from Federal Polytechnic Bida, Nigeria. The present study has provided additional evidence to the growing body of knowledge by suggesting that moral disengagement accounted for a significant amount of variance relative to perceived organisational control in the prediction of workplace deviance. This finding therefore showed that what matter most in predicting workplace deviance is moral disengagement rather than perceived organisational control. Furthermore, the findings of this study extended prior research demonstrating a relationship between perceived organisational control and workplace deviance(de Lara et al., 2006; Kura et al., 2013a), as well as between moral disengagement and workplace deviance (e.g., Christian & Ellis, 2014; Claybourn, 2011).

Although the present study has extended prior research demonstrating a significant relationship between perceived organisational control and workplace deviance, as well as the link between moral disengagement and work place deviance; there are several limitations in

the present study that ought to be acknowledged. First, the present study mainly involved teaching staff from Federal Polytechnic Bida, Nigeria. As such, it may not represent the general population of Nigerian polytechnics. Second, the cross-sectional research design could not allow valid conclusions to be drawn regarding the cause and effect. Additionally, given the dynamic nature of individuals, it is important to employ longitudinal research designs in the future research to better capture the dynamism of the participants in predicting their deviant act in the workplace.

This study concludes that the role of moral disengagement cannot be underrated in predicting workplace deviance. A morally disengaged staff is prone to engage in series of deviant acts unlike employees who are morally engaged. The way forward is for the HR Department to formulate policies and strategies to curb moral decadence among employees.

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